

Title: Incompatibility: How Big Data and Intelligence are drifting away from one another

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INTRODUCTION:

A theoretical exploration how the current approaches to machine learning, deep learning and artificial intelligence are distancing themselves from what we know of human intelligence, specifically in the area of the cognitive sciences.

AIM:

To redress the current approaches of big data processing with the explicit aim to better define and understand intelligence as a whole.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This exploration was heavily influenced by Noam Chomsky's work on generative grammar and the broader domain of psychology, namely Sigmund Freud, Jacques Lacan, Michel Foucault and Slavoj Zizek. Other areas of cognitive science were explored in an effort to be as philosophically complete as possible.

RESULTS:

None apart from convincing a group of data marketers to rethink their approach to their work.

CONCLUSIONS:

That artificial intelligence in a poor articulation of the various approaches and techniques associated to data processing and machine learning.

KEYWORDS:

Artificial Intelligence. Deep Learning. Machine Learning. Big Data. Philosophy. Cognitive Science. Epistemology.

BIOGRAPHY:

Sasha Grujicic – Chief Digital & Strategy Officer – Dentsu Aegis Network

Sasha is an award winning media, marketing and technology executive at Dentsu Aegis Network working with Fortune 500 companies (GM, P&G, adidas, Diageo, Citibank, Disney, Target) to understand people, technology and their connection to their businesses. Helping to manage substantial investments, overseeing annual revenues of over \$60 million and managing over 600 employees globally Sasha has worked the world over integrating the worlds of technology, business, policy, media and ideology.

Actively working on solutions that range from new product and service development, global marketing programs and new technologies Sasha has worked with some of the world's biggest companies from London, New York, Paris, Boston and Toronto. Sasha also serves as an editor and interviewer at the Lab Magazine where he develops features with the world's greatest intellectuals like Noam Chomsky and Amy Goodman.

Sasha is also a graduate of Singularity University, the elite, global joint venture program founded by Google, NASA and a host of leading intellectuals including Ray Kurzweil, dedicated to the understanding of accelerating technologies and their impacts on humanity. One of the most highly regarded of Singularity's recent graduates, Sasha actively consults with a variety of emerging companies dedicated to the adoption of accelerating technologies.

Sasha is a passionate writer, speaker and technology evangelist contributing to publications like Marketing, Strategy, Infopresse and Campaign and lecturing at the Ontario College of Art and Design, the IAB, the World Future Society, Miami Ad School and the University of Ottawa.